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Assessing the Impacts of Cellphones on the Behavior of Children

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ABSTRACT

Cellphones have become central devices of daily use by our new generation. An emergent group of cellphones users [children] who grow up facing the ubiquity of such devices. Yet, little is understood concerning the antecedents and consequences of their cellphone use. In term of consequences, negative effect seems to outweigh the benefits. Especially sleep quality, quantity and cognitive abilities are negatively affected. This paper provides remedial measures for digital detoxification among children.

Keywords: Cellphone addiction, Technology advancement, Effects on Children

INTRODUCTION

A worldwide technology advancement plays a vital role in individual's life. The cell phone today is a life for many. Children get more attracted towards cellphone than the older generation. Now cell phone is considered not only for communication device but it also a necessary social accessory. Children are more inclined towards changing fashion and trends which gave a negative impact on one's life. A number of surveys conducted on children worldwide have figured out that they considered cell phones an integral part of survival and some have ever gone to the extent of saying that they would rather go without food for a day than without their cell phones.

Statement of the Problem

Our today's generation born in an era where smart phones are an important part of our life but as we know addiction of anything is wrong thing. Today

children are not doing well in education due to addiction of cell phones because many children use phones limitlessly. They don't value their time. Their parents give the cell phones when they are busy with work, they use them to play for many hours it will put a lot of stress on children. They don't take interest in their studies. According to doctors, Mobile phone addiction is not different from any other type of addiction (e.g.: - drug). Moreover, children check their phones after every hour during family meals, and even in-between their school homework this will distract children from their studies and leads to poor performance in class. After using phone day and night next day children attend school in a state of exhaustion. They are too tired to concentrate and it affects their learning and behavior.

Research Objectives

1. To explore the causes of allowing cell phones to children.
2. To understand the children, psyche of using cell phones.
3. To forward remedial measure for digital detoxification.

Research Questions

1. What are the causes of allowing cell phone to children?
2. What are the major factors that drive children to use cell phones?
3. How can overuse of cell phones be minimized among children?

Significance of the Study

Due to advancement of technology, it is very serious issue to study this topic. In pandemic [Covid-19], all the children have to had their phones to complete their school work. Parents give phone to children for doing their school work but children rather than doing their school work they get more attractive towards on social media if they want any information, they directly take help from google instead of asking their teachers or parents children started finding solution themselves on phone. This problem creates a huge gap between children and parents. There is nothing wrong in that with the advancement of technology, children becoming more advance. But we have to keep in mind technology is giving us a lot but in return it is taking our whole life from us. Earlier, our grandparents more connected with nature, they live their life to the fullest with no disease but now cell phones make us a home of illness. New diseases spread out due to continuous use of cell phones.

Today life is not possible without cell phones. When we go outside our home, we take someone with us or not but we definitely take our cell phone with us. Cell phone is becoming an important part of our life. The evolution of phones and technology make our life easier, we have so many apps which are useful for us which make our life easy where we can pay our bills, order food online, book tickets for travelling etc. But the problem is serious only when we misuse and use our cell phone limitlessly. This cell phone is affecting

the growth and development of children when they use it without limits. In addition to this, children learn a lot from their surroundings too. when they see that their parents pick up the phone and replies to messages where they unknowingly spend their time more on the phone not realizing to spend time with their children, the Children now feel neglected and start playing with their phone. Children's life is now confined to phone only. Doctors also say that cell phone addiction in children develop anxiety and low self-esteem and also in a few case children die in early ages due to developing bad habits. God gave us very beautiful life but children are going away from virtual world and more attracted towards bad things.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Girela- Serrano BM, Toledano MB [2022], they have studied over the last two years, the communication and the information has changed drastically with the development and rapid un take of new portable device such as cell phones, which are provide instant access to the internet everywhere with the market research reporting 83% of children in the UK aged 12-15 own a cell phone. A child may now enable Internet browsing, games, applications, learning, online communication and social networking.

The growing use of these technologies has raised concern about how exposure patterns may affect children on their mental health disorder. Constitute one of the dominant health problems of this age group and up to 50% of the mental disorder emerge under the age of 15. Children have a constant need to interact and to be acknowledge by other, so that they can define their role and status in the Peer group.

According to Jalila -Al-Balush and Hafedh Al - Shihi (2016) has found out, sometimes parents provide cellphone to their children's is to persuade them to eat. There are many risks or negative impacts associated with the use of cellphone by children." Cyber bullying" is one of them. Cyber bullying as a term is defined as" attempt to use emotional harm and social embarrassment through the use of instant e-mail, text message via cellphones. Another study mentions that the social networks are responsible for creating an environment for cyber bullying especially for girls.

Another risk associated with the use of mobile device by children is "sexual message". Sexual message can have 'unintended consequences ' and many results into harmful or problematic practice for some children take with unknown people this could be to sharing sensitive data with them

METHODOLOGY

The research design of this research is mixed as it has used both Qualitative and Quantative data to collect and analyze the data. In first stage is "Face to face interaction" with parents of children to collect data. The data were refined

based upon the outcomes of the survey validation stage in order to match all the comments which were provided previously. As for sample and Sampling, the data were collected through Stratified random sampling technique. As for methods of data collection, A total of 15 children and their parents participated in the survey using google forms as a web-based questionnaire. Both open ended and close ended types of question were set in the questionnaire. As for methods of data analysis, the data were analysed using descriptive statistics and content analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

98% reported that they regularly check their phones during the night. 97% regularly check their phones whilst doing their homework. 70% discretely check their phones during lesson time. 9% of said that on average they check their phones every two minutes. A survey takes many points of view of children (age 12-17) 1) I like to play games. I like to play and try to beat my score. It is a bit addictive so I am on my phone all the time (age 12). 2)I check my phone to stay in touch with my friends and I like to know going on with my friends (age 16). 3) I like to spend more time on phone rather than playing outside (age 13).

CONCLUSION

Mobile addiction can ruin children's life if it is not stopped on time. Children follows these Remedial measures for digital detoxification mentioned above. Cellphones are causing more harm than good. It is difficult to cop up with the problem immediately, but with the support from family and with proper care of children's can be really helpful in overcoming mobile addiction.

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